

FLAW DETECTION IN COMPOSITES USING SHEAROGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an optical method called 'Shearography' for detecting flaws in a composite material viz glassfibre reinforced plastics. Visual inspection for flaws is allowed by codes although this technique may not be adequate. Shearography is an interferometric method which provides whole-field observation of derivatives of small surface displacements and hence, strains. Since defects in composite structures such as disbonds or delamination usually induce strain concentrations, shearography reveals defects from anomalies in the fringes. Glass fibre reinforced polyester plates are fabricated with known flaw sizes and shapes programmed into them. The "vacuum stressing" method is employed and results show that disbonds in the laminates can be easily located and sized.

INTRODUCTION

In Singapore, the use of composite materials e.g. glassfibre reinforced plastics (GRP) is rapidly gaining popularity. Very often, flaws such as improper bonding, voids etc are present during fabrication while during service, delaminations may subsequently develop. Codes like the Singapore Standard SS245:1981 [1] and the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code Section X [2] allow for visual inspection for poor impregnation, blister etc in GRP. However, visual inspection alone is not adequate to detect improper bonding or delamination. A speckle shearing interferometric technique known as shearography [3] has been developed for small strain measurements but it was found to have potential applications as an industrial tool for nondestructive testing [4]. In shearography, the fringes represent loci of constant displacement gradient thus strains,

which, on comparison with holography [5] will reveal sub-surface flaws better. In this paper, it is shown that shearography can be used to locate and size disbonds in GRP plates.

PRINCIPLES OF SHEAROGRAPHY

Figure 1. Optical arrangement for shearography

Fig 1 shows a typical set-up for shearography. The test object, which is illuminated by an expanded laser beam, is positioned in front of an image-shearing camera. Photographic film/plate is placed in the image plane of the camera in order to record on it the focussed image of the object and, subsequently, the interference fringes. This camera differs from an ordinary camera in that half of its lens is covered by a glass wedge having a small shearing angle. With the presence of the shearing angle, the rays from a point on the object passing through the wedge are mapped onto two points, thus giving a pair of laterally sheared images in the image plane. In other words, as shown in Fig 1, the image-shearing camera will bring the rays scattered from one point $P(x, y, z)$ on the object

surface to meet with those scattered from a neighbouring point $P'(x+\delta x, y, z)$ in the image plane.

It has been shown [4] that, with the undeformed object, the intensity I of the total light field on the image plane is

$$I = 2a^2(1 + \cos \phi) \quad (1)$$

where ϕ represents a random phase angle; and

a is the coherent light amplitude which is assumed equal for the two neighbouring points.

Similarly, when the object is deformed, an optical path change occurs due to surface displacements, and the associated intensity I' on the image plane is given by

$$I' = 2a^2[1 + \cos(\phi + \Delta)] \quad (2)$$

where Δ is the relative phase change due to relative displacement between $P'(x + \delta x, y, z)$ and $P(x, y, z)$.

If a photographic film in the image plane is sequentially exposed to intensities I and I' , the total intensity I_s recorded is

$$I_s = I + I' = 4a^2[1 + \cos(\phi + \frac{\Delta}{2}) \cdot \cos \frac{\Delta}{2}] \quad (3)$$

The second term of Eq. 3 represents a high-frequency carrier amplitude modulated by a low-frequency factor $\cos(\Delta/2)$. The high-frequency carrier is nulled when $\Delta = (2N + 1)\pi$, where $N = 0, 1, 2 \dots$ is the fringe order.

The doubly-exposed photographic film is processed and it is called a shearogram. However, the fringes recorded on it are of a frequency variation type and are not readily visible to the eye. They can be made visible by means of a high-pass filter which, in practice, may readily be achieved by viewing the shearogram through a strong light source such as the light from a slide projector. A simple optical arrangement employed to perform the filtering process is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. High pass Fourier filtering set-up

For a small shearing angle, Δ is related to the displacement derivatives by [4]

$$\Delta = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \left[A \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + B \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + C \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right] \delta x \quad (4)$$

where u , v and w represent the displacement components of the point $P(x, y, z)$; A , B and C are related to the position of the illumination point $S(x_s, y_s, z_s)$ and the camera position $O(x_o, y_o, z_o)$ by

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \left(\frac{x - x_o}{R_o} + \frac{x - x_s}{R_s} \right) \\ B &= \left(\frac{y - y_o}{R_o} + \frac{y - y_s}{R_s} \right) \\ C &= \left(\frac{z - z_o}{R_o} + \frac{z - z_s}{R_s} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $R_o^2 = x_o^2 + y_o^2 + z_o^2$

and $R_s^2 = x_s^2 + y_s^2 + z_s^2$

For the present experiment, the illumination and viewing are made normal to the object and R_o and R_s are large compared with the object size. Then, it can be deduced that

$$\Delta = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} (\delta x) \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \quad (6)$$

Eq. 6 shows that fringes are whole-field representation of the loci of constant $\partial w / \partial x$.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

In the present study, woven roving glass reinforced polyester (GRP) flat plates of about 270 mm by 250 mm were fabricated using the usual hand lay-up method. To simulate disbonds or delaminations in these plates, melinex air pockets were created at different layers within the plates during fabrication. The shapes and sizes of these flaws are shown in Fig. 3. Flaw 1 is between the first and second layer, flaw 2 between second

Figure 3. Layout of flaws

and third and so on. The first layer referred to in this context is the one nearest to the surface illuminated by the laser. During the test, the GRP plate was placed in a specially constructed transparent vacuum chamber. A 15mW He Ne laser was used to illuminate the plate specimens. The image-shearing camera used was a Mamiya RB67 Pro-S with a specially ground wedge, of about 1° included angle, placed in the iris plane of the lens. Two exposures were made: one when the plate was at atmospheric pressure and the other when a partial vacuum of 40 mm Hg was introduced. Other different vacuum pressures at 80 mm Hg and 160 mm Hg were also used for loading. All the recordings were done on Kodak high speed holographic plates. The high-pass Fourier filtering set-up used to view the processed plates consisted simply of a slide projector as the light source and the output was recorded by an ordinary 35 mm camera.

Further work was carried out to relate the number of fringes of each flaw to its depth in the GRP plate. The plate was sliced through at the locations of the flaws. A travelling microscope was used to measure the depth of these flaws, taking the illuminated surface of the plate as the datum.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4. Shearogram of GRP plate with circular flaws located at different layers

Fig. 4 shows the image recorded on a shearogram of a 6-ply GRP plate with 5 circular flaws 25 mm diameter located at different layers of the laminate. Partial vacuum pressure of 80 mm Hg was applied. The overall thickness of the plate is approximately 3 mm. The surface deformation gradient of the flaws at different layers can be distinguished quite readily from the shearogram. Fringes obtained from flaw 1 are too dense which is expected because it is nearest to the illuminated surface. However, on comparing flaw 2 and flaw 3 which were located between second/third layer and third/fourth layer respectively, it can be observed that fringes at 2 are denser than 3. This is expected because the disbond nearer the illuminating surface tends to deform more, and higher degree of surface displacement is characterised by the increase in fringe density. The boundary of the defect is well defined especially those nearer the illuminated surface thus making it possible to size the defect. The defect size is measured from the photograph and scaled up according to the standard grid size drawn at the bottom left hand corner of the plate. The amount of vertical shear can be evaluated from this grid as well. The defect size using this method agrees quite well with the actual programmed size.

The relative depth of the disbonds in the laminates can be estimated from the fringe number chart obtained as shown in Figs 5 and 6.

Figure 5. Relationship of depth of circular flaws with number of fringes

Figure 6. Relationship of depth of triangular flaws with number of fringes

NB: Theoretically, the fringe number should be an integer. In our experiment, there are cases where the fringes have formed but not fully. For such cases, they are assigned as fractional fringes.

CONCLUSION

Shearography provides a whole-field observation of displacement gradient in the GRP plates and allows defects to be located and sized. It is non-contacting and does not require any scanning unlike the ultrasonic C-scan. It is found that vacuum stressing is a good method for detecting disbonds in laminates. Such a technique can be used as a check for quality of GRP components.

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